

Disentangling Hardware Embodiment and Trajectory Kinematics During Human-Robot Spatial Negotiation

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Abstract—Effective human-aware motion planning requires understanding how humans adapt their spatial behavior when sharing a workspace with collaborative robots. This study investigates human avoidance behavior during human–robot spatial interaction as a dual-factor process, distinguishing between (i) a static influence related to robot embodiment and mounting configuration, and (ii) a dynamic influence related to trajectory characteristics. We conducted a repeated-measures experiment ($N = 48$) in which participants interacted with a robot executing trajectories with varying approach directions (e.g., head-on vs. parallel) and curvature profiles (Rectilinear vs. Curvilinear), as well as different mounting configurations (table-mounted vs. shoulder-mounted). Human responses were evaluated using continuous kinematic tracking and subjective workload assessment (NASA-TLX). The results indicate systematic differences in human spatial behavior depending on trajectory type and interaction geometry. Rectilinear trajectories were associated with increased subjective workload, altered movement timing, and expanded spatial clearance behavior, particularly in head-on interaction conditions. In contrast, Curvilinear trajectories tended to support more consistent human motion patterns during shared workspace negotiation, despite occupying larger spatial volume. Additionally, robot mounting configuration influenced perceived and behavioral safety margins, with table-mounted setups leading to increased proxemic distance even in the absence of explicit task disruption. This work provides an empirical characterization of how static and dynamic aspects of robot behavior jointly influence human spatial adaptation in shared environments, supporting the design of ergonomically informed human–robot interaction systems.

Index Terms—Human-Robot Interaction, Human-Aware Motion Planning, Trajectory Planning, Shared Workspaces, Collaborative Robots, Proxemics, Cognitive Workload.

I. INTRODUCTION

COLLABORATIVE robots (cobots) increasingly share industrial workspaces with humans, relying on motion planning policies for safe operation [1]. Although human-aware planning has advanced social navigation [2], prevailing international safety standards for industrial robotics [3], [4] and technical specifications for collaborative operations [5] still mandate strict distance-based separation. While these geometric constraints effectively prevent physical collisions [6], [7], they insufficiently account for the cognitive and behavioral adaptations imposed on human operators [8].

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Prior research has optimized trajectory legibility [9] and modeled interpersonal proxemics in human-robot interaction [10]. However, human spatial negotiation depends on more than trajectory geometry alone. The interpretation of robotic motion is inherently shaped by the robot’s physical embodiment, mounting location, and perceived spatial footprint [11]. For example, a table-mounted manipulator occupies a substantially different psychological and spatial presence than an overhead-mounted system executing the identical motion. Therefore, individuals respond simultaneously to both the robot’s static embodiment and its dynamic trajectory, making human avoidance behavior a dual-axis spatial negotiation. Ignoring this physical context risks optimizing robotic efficiency at the expense of human comfort and unhindered movement behavior.

Previous HRI studies have often examined hardware embodiment, proxemics, and trajectory planning independently. To bridge this gap, this study evaluates their interacting behavioral penalties within a unified experimental framework. We operationally divide robotic spatial interference into two measurable dimensions: a *static embodiment penalty*, defined as the baseline proxemic expansion (quantified via minimum proxemic clearance) associated with the robot’s mounting configuration, and a *dynamic behavioral penalty*, defined as the acute cognitive load [12], disrupted temporal synchronization [16], and expansion of the max spatial envelope associated with the robot’s trajectory profile.

To maintain conceptual clarity, we strictly differentiate between human behavioral responses and robotic optimization objectives. Terms such as *kinematic penalty* or *embodiment penalty* are used operationally to denote empirically observable, macro-level human adaptations to shared-workspace negotiation. These measured variables are not assumed to represent explicit internal optimization objectives of the human central nervous system. Rather, they serve as the empirical foundation required to define the mathematical costs (e.g., $J_{\text{kinematic}}$, $J_{\text{embodiment}}$) in future human-aware trajectory planners.

This framework addresses a central trade-off in collaborative motion planning. Rectilinear trajectories minimize absolute path length and execution time but correspond to significant kinematic penalties, including the expansion of the human’s max spatial envelope. In contrast, Curvilinear trajectories may consume greater workspace area while being associated with more direct routing patterns and minimizing disrupted temporal coordination. To investigate these effects alongside

baseline negative attitudes toward robots [13], we conducted a controlled within-subjects experiment manipulating trajectory curvature (Curvilinear vs. Rectilinear), spatial congruency (converging vs. parallel motion), and mounting configuration (shoulder-mounted vs. table-mounted). Linear Mixed-Effects Models (LMMs) [14] were used to account for inter-individual variability in spatial behavior.

By measuring the interaction between embodiment and kinematics during spatial negotiation, we provide an empirical foundation for multi-objective, ergonomically informed trajectory generation. The present work intentionally focuses on the macroscopic behavioral outcomes of spatial negotiation, such as absolute proxemic clearance, max spatial envelope expansion, subjective cognitive load, and temporal synchronization, rather than the continuous kinematic structure of the underlying movement variability.

II. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

A. Participants

A total of $N = 48$ participants ($M_{\text{age}} = 24.2$, $SD = 5.8$ years; 50% female, 50% male) were recruited, primarily from a university population.

Baseline psychological assessments (measured via 5-point Likert scales) indicated low prior experience with robots generally ($M = 2.35$, $SD = 1.14$) and robotic arms specifically ($M = 1.67$, $SD = 1.15$), but moderate familiarity with virtual agents via video games ($M = 3.44$, $SD = 1.24$). The majority of the cohort (87.5%) was right-handed. Participants were screened to ensure no developmental or movement disabilities, and all performed the required task movements using their right arm to standardize the kinematic data. All participants provided written informed consent, and the protocol was approved by the University Ethics Committee.

Table I summarizes participant demographics and baseline covariates. Although the full Negative Attitudes Toward Robots Scale (NARS) was administered, Subscale 1 (Interaction Anxiety) was isolated *a priori* as the primary covariate for spatial negotiation. This specific subscale isolates apprehension toward physical proximity and direct interaction. Notably, the items were scored from 1 = “I agree completely” to 5 = “I completely disagree”. Because the subscale statements describe negative reactions (e.g., feeling uncomfortable or nervous), higher numerical scores on this axis reflect *lower* baseline apprehension. The observed cohort mean ($M = 4.06$, $SD = 0.55$) indicates a generally high baseline comfort level regarding robotic interaction.

TABLE I
PARTICIPANT DEMOGRAPHICS & BASELINE COVARIATES

Metric	Value
Total Participants (N)	48
Age Range	18–46 years
Mean Age (SD)	24.2 (± 5.8)
Gender Breakdown	24 Male, 24 Female
Handedness	42 Right, 6 Left
Baseline Covariates (Likert 1–5)	
Mean Virtual Familiarity (SD)	3.44 (± 1.24)
Mean NARS Subscale 1 (SD)	4.06 (± 0.55)

B. Hypotheses

We formulated three primary hypotheses:

- **H1 (Trajectory Profiling):** Incongruent spatial direction (converging approaches) and Rectilinear trajectory profiles will elicit greater subjective cognitive load (NASA-TLX) and an expanded max spatial envelope compared to parallel, Curvilinear paths.
- **H2 (The Kinematic Trade-off):** Despite Rectilinear paths minimizing absolute Euclidean distance, Curvilinear trajectories will better preserve the human’s forward kinematic path ratio and minimize disrupted temporal coordination.
- **H3 (Embodiment Constraints):** Transitioning the hardware origin from a shoulder-mounted to a table-mounted configuration will correspond to a baseline expansion of the human’s proxemic safety boundary (minimum proxemic clearance), and this static embodiment penalty will be significantly magnified by dynamic spatial conflict (converging approaches).

C. Study Design and Experimental Setup

The experiment was conducted using a UR3 robot arm (Universal Robots®, Denmark), illustrated in Figure 1. The study employed a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ repeated-measures factorial design manipulating three primary variables: *Spatial Congruency* (same-side vs. opposite-side), *Trajectory Shape* (Curvilinear vs. Rectilinear), and *Hardware Origin* (shoulder vs. table).

Fig. 1. Wide view of the experimental setup, illustrating the participant’s placement relative to the robot arm, the optical tracking system, and the pick-and-place targets.

Each participant completed two experimental blocks, one for each hardware origin. The block order was counterbalanced between participants ($n = 24$ per group). Within each block, the four software conditions (Congruency \times Trajectory) were fully crossed and presented using balanced Latin-square sequences [15] (see Table II and Figure 2). In each condition, participants performed 15 reciprocal pick-and-place repetitions in synchrony with the deterministic motion of the robot [16],

TABLE II
BALANCED LATIN-SQUARE SEQUENCES (A–D) USED TO ORDER THE WITHIN-BLOCK CONDITIONS.

Sequence	Order 1	Order 2	Order 3	Order 4
A	SC	OC	OR	SR
B	OC	SR	SC	OR
C	SR	OR	OC	SC
D	OR	SC	SR	OC

Note: SC=Same-side/Curvilinear, OC=Opposite-side/Curvilinear, SR=Same-side/Rectilinear, OR=Opposite-side/Rectilinear.

a task profile known to elicit measurable progression in hand trajectory variability [17].

Spatial Congruency: Both agents began from the lower platform in the *same-side* (parallel) condition. In the *opposite-side* (converging) condition, the human started from the upper platform while the robot started from the lower, inducing a head-on spatial conflict.

Hardware Origin: The robot was reconfigured between a standard table-mounted position (base affixed to the shared planar workspace) and an elevated, side-mounted position on an aluminum frame. This frame structurally approximates the physical presence of a human collaborator, with the robot base aligned approximately at the human operator’s shoulder height (hereafter referred to as “shoulder-mounted”). This configuration altered the physical embodiment and base workspace footprint, introducing variations in visual approach angles, spatial occlusion, and looming perception.

Trajectory Shape: The robot’s movement profile was manipulated to execute either continuous Curvilinear sweeps or piecewise Rectilinear translations (the mathematical generation of these profiles is detailed formally in Section II-D).

D. Trajectory Profiling and Generation

To isolate spatial variables from temporal confounds, both Curvilinear and Rectilinear profiles were mathematically locked to an identical spatiotemporal framework. Both paths shared identical origin, via-point, and termination coordinates (forming two orthogonal 300 mm segments). Both executed in exactly 2.0 s, reaching the via-point at $t = 1.0$ s.

To ensure kinematic smoothness, both profiles were generated using a 5th-order polynomial basis function to minimize jerk (the third derivative of position) [18]:

$$\mathbf{p}(t) = \mathbf{c}_5 t^5 + \mathbf{c}_4 t^4 + \mathbf{c}_3 t^3 + \mathbf{c}_2 t^2 + \mathbf{c}_1 t + \mathbf{c}_0 \quad (1)$$

While the temporal boundaries and optimization basis were identical, spatial geometry was manipulated via waypoint constraints:

- **Curvilinear Profile (Continuous Momentum):** The transport motion was generated as a single, coupled sequence. The solver enforced strict continuity (position, velocity, acceleration, jerk, and snap) at the via-point. Omitting a zero-velocity constraint allowed continuous momentum to carry the end-effector through the waypoint, yielding a continuous Curvilinear trajectory.
- **Rectilinear Profile (Piecewise Translation):** The transport motion was severed into two independent segments. By injecting strict zero-velocity and zero-acceleration

Fig. 2. Comprehensive spatial footprint of the human-robot negotiation across the evaluated conditions. Robot reference trajectories (green) and the resulting human kinematic adaptations (yellow) are overlaid in a 2×2 matrix. **Columns (Hardware Embodiment):** The side-mounted frame (left) minimizes visual occlusion of the shared workspace. Conversely, the table-mounted base (right) intrinsically alters approach vectors, introduces workspace occlusion, and elevates perceived looming. **Rows (Trajectory Kinematics):** Rectilinear paths (top) minimize absolute distance but are associated with an expanded max spatial envelope, while Curvilinear paths (bottom) sweep a larger area but allow the human to preserve more direct routing. The density of the plotted human spatial envelopes visually captures the compounded penalties of these bundled hardware and software variables.

constraints at the intermediate via-point ($\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{0}$, $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{0}$), the robot executed a direct linear translation (minimizing Euclidean distance), stopped entirely, rotated its velocity vector, and executed the second linear translation.

Because the temporal phase alignment was locked ($t = 1.0$ s at the via-point), a necessary velocity trade-off emerged. Because the Rectilinear profile forces the robot to traverse a longer orthogonal path (which includes the mandatory stop at the apex) within the exact same temporal duration as the Curvilinear profile (2.0 s), it inherently demands substantially higher kinematics. Specifically, the Rectilinear motion requires a peak velocity of 0.56 m/s and a peak acceleration of 1.73 m/s², representing roughly a 20% and 22% increase over the Curvilinear baseline (0.47 m/s and 1.41 m/s²). By neutralizing absolute task-completion time as a potential confound, this mathematical constraint ensures that human behavioral responses reflect the combined reality of the trajectory’s orthogonal shape and its necessarily more aggressive acceleration profile, rather than differences in total

execution time.

E. Data Acquisition and Processing

Object and limb kinematics were recorded at 120 Hz using an OptiTrack Trio[®] system and processed via a custom MATLAB pipeline. Missing data were reconstructed using linear interpolation with nearest-neighbor edge padding.

To ensure spatial comparability across hardware configurations, the camera frame was translated to the robot’s initial end-effector position, establishing a universal spatial origin. Coordinate frames were then aligned to the shared task space to isolate planar routing, formally defining the x -axis as the frontal depth vector (robot-to-human) and the y -axis as the orthogonal lateral vector. Finally, kinematic trajectories were smoothed using a second-order, zero-phase Butterworth low-pass filter (6 Hz cutoff) to isolate voluntary human motor control from sensor jitter, establishing the standardized coordinate space required to extract the dual-axis spatial metrics.

F. Measures and Statistical Aggregation

To account for temporal autocorrelation and motor adaptation across the 15 reciprocal repetitions, trial-level kinematic data were aggregated per condition block for each participant prior to LMM inference. The dependent measures were defined as follows:

1) *Spatial Proxemics and Avoidance*: Because the robot’s deterministic rhythm inherently phase-locked the human’s motion, we quantified behavioral displacement directly, avoiding temporal distortion algorithms (e.g., Dynamic Time Warping). Instead, we extracted two key spatial metrics to formalize the dual-axis spatial negotiation framework (Figure 3):

- **Max Spatial Envelope (Axis 1 - Dynamic/Lateral)**: Defined as the total orthogonal spread of the bounding box encapsulating the human’s path. This metric captures the absolute lateral operational footprint forced by the robot’s dynamic trajectory.
- **Minimum Proxemic Clearance (Axis 2 - Static/Depth)**: Defined as the absolute closest 3D Euclidean distance maintained between the human’s arm and the robot’s end-effector during the active transport phase. This metric quantifies the raw physical violation of the human’s personal safety boundary dictated by the hardware’s static embodiment. Across all reported metrics, directionality is standardized: higher numerical values indicate that the human maintained a greater absolute physical distance (a wider safety margin) from the robotic agent.

2) *Task Efficacy and Kinematic Adaptation*: To evaluate the impact of the robotic trajectories on task execution and physical routing, we extracted two objective metrics:

- **2D Planar Endpoint Precision**: The area of the 95% confidence ellipse derived from the final object placement coordinates on the target surface (xy -plane).
- **Kinematic Path Ratio (η)**: To formalize the degree of human spatial adaptation (central to H2), η is defined as the dimensionless ratio of the human’s actual integrated

Methodology: Dynamic Spatial Bounds by Congruency

Fig. 3. Empirical definitions of the dual-axis spatial boundaries. **(Left)** Extreme Converging (opposite-side) conflict, demonstrating a pronounced expansion of the human’s Max Spatial Envelope. **(Right)** Extreme Parallel (same-side) tracking, demonstrating a highly constrained spatial envelope. Minimum Proxemic Clearance (dashed line) acts as the absolute 3D Euclidean boundary in both states.

path length to the robot’s programmed reference path length:

$$\eta = \frac{d_{\text{actual}}}{d_{\text{reference}}} = \frac{\int_{t_0}^{t_f} \|\mathbf{v}_{\text{human}}(t)\| dt}{\int_{t_0}^{t_f} \|\mathbf{v}_{\text{robot}}(t)\| dt} \quad (2)$$

where d_{actual} is the integrated 3D arc length executed by the human hand, and $d_{\text{reference}}$ is the corresponding arc length of the deterministic robotic trajectory. A value of $\eta = 1.0$ indicates that the human mirrored the reference arc length. Because human motor control inherently optimizes reaching movements by executing direct point-to-point translations rather than rigidly tracking orthogonal waypoints, values of $\eta < 1.0$ indicate a shorter, more direct human path. Consequently, deviations further below 1.0 directly quantify the magnitude of spatial adaptation required to negotiate the robotic interference.

3) *Continuous Interference Predictor (Simultaneous Motion Ratio)*: To quantify dynamic interference, we defined the *Simultaneous Motion Ratio (SMR)*. Because human avoidance in these tasks typically manifests as abrupt, intermittent pausing rather than continuous oscillatory coupling, SMR serves as an operational proxy for episodic pausing. It is evaluated via a Boolean velocity state across the interaction phase:

$$\text{SMR} = \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \delta_i \right) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where N is the total number of frames during the synchronized motion phase, and the indicator variable $\delta_i = 1$ if both the instantaneous human hand velocity ($\|\mathbf{v}_{\text{human}}\|$) and robot end-effector velocity ($\|\mathbf{v}_{\text{robot}}\|$) exceed their respective thresholds (τ), and 0 otherwise.

To isolate intentional transport motion from motor stabilization noise, dynamic velocity thresholds (τ_{human} and τ_{robot}) were defined as 10% of the peak velocity for each specific trial. This relative thresholding approach normalizes individual baseline

variance, ensuring the metric captures acute interaction effects rather than absolute speed differences or programmatic acceleration ramps.

4) *Subjective Evaluation*: Subjective psychological responses were evaluated across three distinct temporal stages of the experiment. Baseline interaction anxiety was measured *a priori* using the Negative Attitudes Toward Robots Scale (NARS) [13]. Following each dynamic experimental condition, acute cognitive load was assessed via the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) [12], paired with a Post-Condition Evaluation Questionnaire (PCEQ) consisting of 5-point Likert items evaluating synchronization difficulty and perceived human-likeness of the trajectory. Finally, to isolate the static embodiment penalty, participants completed a block-level assessment evaluating generalized spatial disturbance following the conclusion of each hardware configuration block.

III. RESULTS

To evaluate the dual-axis spatial negotiation framework, the data were analyzed across our primary behavioral metrics. The omnibus statistical outcomes for all Linear Mixed-Effects Models (LMMs) are summarized in Table III.

A. Statistical Analysis Approach

Kinematic and subjective data were analyzed in R (v4.6.0; *lme4*, *lmerTest*). To account for baseline variance in individual biomechanics, data were modeled using Linear Mixed-Effects Models (LMMs) fit via Restricted Maximum Likelihood (REML) [14].

To isolate dynamic spatial negotiation from terminal targeting kinematics, all continuous physical interaction metrics (Max Spatial Envelope and Minimum Proxemic Clearance) were strictly evaluated within the “cruising phase,” defined as the central 80% (10%–90%) of the transport trajectory. This isolation successfully removes baseline variance artificially induced by physical anchoring at the required drop zones. Furthermore, because the forward and return transport phases represent geometrically symmetrical interactions, statistical models were restricted to the initial transport phase (Motion 1) as the representative trial to prevent redundant dimensional compounding in the mixed-effects models.

The full-factorial model was specified *a priori* across all primary dependent variables: $\text{Outcome} \sim \text{Congruency} * \text{Trajectory_Shape} * \text{Hardware_Origin} + (1 | \text{Participant})$. To ensure main effect estimates and β coefficients accurately reflect omnibus significance in the presence of higher-order interactions, all factors were evaluated using orthogonal sum-to-zero contrasts (*contr.sum*). Consequently, model *p*-values reflect Type III Sum of Squares.

Initial maximal models including within-subject random slopes consistently resulted in singular fits. Following principled simplification guidelines [19], models were reduced to include only random intercepts for participants. Degrees of freedom were estimated using the Satterthwaite approximation.

Model assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity were verified via residual diagnostics prior to inference. Post-hoc pairwise contrasts were evaluated via Estimated Marginal Means (*M*) at $\alpha = 0.05$ with Tukey adjustments for multiple comparisons. Overall fixed-effect variance was quantified using Marginal R^2 (R_m^2) [20]. For pairwise contrasts, standardized effect sizes (d_{LMM}) were computed by dividing the estimated marginal mean difference by the model’s residual standard deviation (σ). This d_{LMM} metric represents the experimental effect magnitude relative to the raw, unadjusted variance of the human kinematic data.

B. H1: Trajectory Profiling and Spatial Displacement

The results supported H1 predictions. Rectilinear trajectory profiles and converging approach angles were associated with higher reported cognitive load and consistently expanded spatial envelopes; however, these physical and psychological penalties proved to be highly context-dependent.

Subjective Cognitive Load (NASA-TLX): The LMM analysis revealed that both spatial congruency (Estimate = 1.98, 95% CI [1.29, 2.66], $p < 0.001$) and algorithmically efficient Rectilinear trajectories (Estimate = 1.08, 95% CI [0.39, 1.77], $p = 0.002$) incurred measurable cognitive penalties. A significant interaction qualified these main effects (Estimate = 1.01, 95% CI [0.33, 1.70], $p = 0.004$). As illustrated in Figure 4A, while head-on approaches intrinsically raise cognitive load, the penalty is significantly magnified when the robot executes a Rectilinear trajectory that directly violates the user’s forward spatial envelope.

Max Spatial Envelope: Physical avoidance behavior during the cruising phase further formalized the context-dependent nature of human spatial negotiation. Figure 4B illustrates the mean Max Spatial Envelope. The LMM confirmed a highly significant main effect of *Spatial Congruency* (Estimate = 47.92, 95% CI [42.46, 53.37], $p < 0.001$), establishing that converging approaches consistently correspond to an expansion of the human’s lateral operational footprint. Additionally, the main effect of *Trajectory Shape* (Estimate = -14.25 , 95% CI [-19.71 , -8.80], $p < 0.001$) was qualified by a significant interaction (Estimate = 5.92, 95% CI [0.47, 11.37], $p = 0.034$).

Under converging approaches, Rectilinear trajectories were associated with a significantly greater expansion of the human’s spatial envelope than Curvilinear trajectories. During parallel tracking where spatial conflict is mitigated, this dynamic behavioral penalty was substantially reduced.

While this Max Spatial Envelope captures the absolute macroscopic boundary of the human’s avoidance behavior, the continuous internal structure of this geometric deviation, specifically how variance expands dynamically relative to the distractor axis, is evaluated in our parallel kinematic analysis [21], where the same interaction is evaluated through Distractor-Aligned Variance and biomechanical adaptation metrics.

Continuous Synchronization Predictor: An LMM incorporating the continuous *Simultaneous Motion Ratio* found no significant predictive relationship with overall cognitive load (Estimate = -0.028 , SE = 0.080, $t(341) = -0.35$, $p = 0.727$).

TABLE III
OMNIBUS LINEAR MIXED-EFFECTS MODELS (LMM) SUMMARY FOR PRIMARY DEPENDENT VARIABLES

Dependent Variable	Fixed Effect	Estimate (β)	95% CI	t -value	p -value	R_m^2
Cognitive Load (NASA-TLX)	Trajectory Shape (Rectilinear)	1.08	[0.39, 1.77]	3.08	0.002	0.024
	Spatial Congruency (Converging)	1.98	[1.29, 2.66]	5.64	< 0.001	
	Interaction (Traj \times Cong)	1.01	[0.33, 1.70]	2.89	0.004	
Temporal Synchronization (SMR %)	Trajectory Shape (Rectilinear)	-3.18	[-3.65, -2.71]	-13.34	< 0.001	0.240
	Spatial Congruency (Converging)	-0.62	[-1.08, -0.15]	-2.58	0.010	
	Interaction (Traj \times Cong)	-0.81	[-1.28, -0.34]	-3.40	< 0.001	
Max Spatial Envelope (Lateral, mm)	Spatial Congruency (Converging)	47.92	[42.46, 53.37]	17.22	< 0.001	0.485
	Trajectory Shape (Rectilinear)	-14.25	[-19.71, -8.80]	-5.12	< 0.001	
	Interaction (Traj \times Cong)	5.92	[0.47, 11.37]	2.13	0.034	
Minimum Proxemic Clearance (mm)	Hardware Origin (Table Mount)	1.88	[0.77, 2.99]	3.32	< 0.001	0.031
	Spatial Congruency (Converging)	1.44	[0.33, 2.54]	2.53	0.012	
	Interaction (Hard \times Cong)	1.19	[0.08, 2.29]	2.09	0.037	

Note: Kinematic spatial models (Max Spatial Envelope and Proxemic Clearance) evaluate the mid-trajectory cruising phase (10%–90%) to isolate active spatial negotiation from terminal targeting variance. Estimates (β) represent unstandardized model coefficients derived via orthogonal sum-to-zero contrasts. Confidence Intervals (CI) are calculated at the 95% level using the Wald method. The p -values reflect omnibus Type III Sum of Squares.

Fig. 4. Behavioral and subjective metrics across trajectory profiles. (A) NASA-TLX overall subjective cognitive load scores. The cognitive penalty of Rectilinear motion is primarily present during converging (opposite) approaches. (B) Max Spatial Envelope across evaluated conditions, highlighting the systematic lateral expansion associated with converging Rectilinear paths. (***) $p < 0.001$, (**) $p < 0.01$, NS = Not Significant).

The absence of a direct predictive relationship suggests a theoretical decoupling: while Rectilinear trajectories contextually trigger both disrupted temporal coordination and elevated cognitive load in converging scenarios, the episodic pausing itself does not directly drive the subjective penalty. Rather, they manifest as parallel, distinct symptoms of the underlying spatial conflict.

C. H2: Kinematic Optimization vs. Human Routing

The results supported H2. The data revealed a geometric trade-off between minimizing the robot’s absolute Euclidean distance and preserving the human’s kinematic path ratio, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Curvilinear paths swept a significantly larger absolute planar area ($M = 29\,125\text{ mm}^2$) than the distance-minimizing Rectilinear paths ($M = 26\,512\text{ mm}^2$; Difference = 2613 mm^2 , 95% CI [633, 4593], $p = 0.010$, $d_{LMM} = 0.28$). However, an LMM evaluating human kinematic path execution demonstrated that Curvilinear trajectories promoted closer spatial adherence, with the human closely mirroring the robot’s reference arc ($\eta = 0.932$). In contrast, the orthogonal geometry of the

Rectilinear paths corresponded to a greater divergence from the robot’s reference path; humans executed more pronounced shortcuts to negotiate the spatial interference, resulting in a significantly lower path ratio ($\eta = 0.868$; Estimate = -0.064 , 95% CI [$-0.083, -0.045$], $p < 0.001$, $d_{LMM} = 0.72$). Under Rectilinear conditions, participants executed spatial shortcuts representing an approximate 13% deviation ($1 - \eta$) from the robot’s reference path, nearly double the deviation observed in Curvilinear trials.

Fig. 5. Spatial geometry comparisons. (A) Absolute planar area consumed by Curvilinear vs. Rectilinear trajectories. (B) Corresponding kinematic path ratio (η) observed under each condition, illustrating human kinematic path preservation (***) $p < 0.001$.

Subjective Evaluation (PCEQ): Post-condition surveys indicated that participants rated the Curvilinear paths as significantly less disruptive to synchronize with (Estimate = -0.35 , 95% CI [$-0.51, -0.20$], $p < 0.001$) and rated them higher on the “human-like” motion scale ($M = 2.86$) compared to Rectilinear paths ($M = 2.00$; Difference = 0.86 , 95% CI [0.70, 1.01], $p < 0.001$). Full per-condition PCEQ main effects are reported in Table IV.

1) *Task Efficacy and Temporal Synchronization:* In addition to psychological and spatial penalties, we assessed whether spatial interference degraded industrial task execution.

Task Efficacy (Endpoint Precision): The LMM analysis

TABLE IV
LMM MAIN EFFECTS RESULTS FOR PER-CONDITION SUBJECTIVE
QUESTIONS (PCEQ).

Dependent Variable	Fixed Effect	F-value	p-value
Harder to Synchronize With	Spatial Congruency	39.32	< 0.001***
	Trajectory Shape	22.44	< 0.001***
	Hardware Origin	0.49	0.486
Perceived as Human-like	Spatial Congruency	0.72	0.395
	Trajectory Shape	116.65	< 0.001***
	Hardware Origin	2.68	0.103

Note: Degrees of freedom for all F -statistics are (1, 329). *** $p < 0.001$. Two-way and three-way interactions were evaluated; no significant three-way interactions were observed across PCEQ metrics.

for 2D Planar Endpoint Precision revealed a significant interaction between *Spatial Congruency* and *Trajectory Shape* ($F(1, 333) = 8.31, p = 0.004, R_m^2 = 0.022$).

Under parallel (same-side) approaches, placement precision remained stable regardless of the trajectory profile ($p = 0.899$). However, under converging (opposite-side) approaches, Rectilinear paths were associated with a significant reduction in placement precision ($M = 116.5 \text{ mm}^2$) compared to Curvilinear paths ($M = 73.9 \text{ mm}^2$; Difference = 42.7 mm^2 , 95% CI [21.5, 63.9], $p < 0.001, d_{LMM} = 0.57$).

Temporal Synchronization (Simultaneous Motion): Temporal efficiency was evaluated via the *Simultaneous Motion Ratio* (SMR). The LMM revealed highly significant main effects for both *Trajectory Shape* (Estimate = -3.18 , 95% CI [$-3.65, -2.71$], $p < 0.001$) and *Spatial Congruency* (Estimate = -0.62 , 95% CI [$-1.08, -0.15$], $p = 0.010$). In addition, a significant interaction (Estimate = -0.81 , 95% CI [$-1.28, -0.34$], $p < 0.001$) demonstrated that temporal coordination is most severely disrupted when Rectilinear geometries are deployed during head-on spatial conflicts, leading to significant drops in simultaneous motion and increased episodic pausing.

D. H3: Embodiment Constraints and Baseline Proxemics

The data partially supported H3. While the robot’s mounting configuration altered the human’s physical proxemic safety boundaries, it did not significantly affect generalized psychological disturbance.

Generalized Disturbance: Block-level post-condition surveys evaluating generalized spatial intrusion revealed no statistically significant main effect for *Hardware Origin* ($F(1, 47) = 2.40, p = 0.128$). While the table-mounted configuration trended toward a slightly higher subjective sense of disturbance ($M = 6.30$) compared to the shoulder-mounted configuration ($M = 6.12$), this difference did not reach significance.

Static Embodiment Penalty and Proxemics: Despite the lack of a generalized subjective penalty, the hardware origin strongly dictated physical proxemic adaptation (Figure 6A). The main effect of hardware origin on minimum proxemic safety clearance during the cruising phase was highly significant ($M_{\text{table}} = 213 \text{ mm}$ vs. $M_{\text{shoulder}} = 209 \text{ mm}$; Estimate =

1.88, 95% CI [0.77, 2.99], $p < 0.001$). The main effect of spatial congruency was also significant (Estimate = 1.44, 95% CI [0.33, 2.54], $p = 0.012$). The LMM also revealed a significant interaction between *Hardware Origin* and *Spatial Congruency* (Estimate = 1.19, 95% CI [0.08, 2.29], $p = 0.037$).

Mirroring the kinematic penalties observed in H1, the physical embodiment penalty was heavily magnified by head-on conflict. During converging approaches, the table-mounted robot was associated with a significant expansion of the human’s spatial safety buffer ($M = 215 \text{ mm}$) compared to the shoulder-mounted system ($M = 209 \text{ mm}$). However, during parallel approaches, this hardware-driven clearance difference collapsed almost entirely ($M_{\text{table}} = 210 \text{ mm}$ vs. $M_{\text{shoulder}} = 209 \text{ mm}$). As shown in Figure 6B, the minimum proxemic clearance exhibited no significant main effect across trajectory shapes ($p = 0.872$). This confirms that raw depth-avoidance is primarily associated with the hardware’s static intrusion interacting with the approach vector, rather than the trajectory’s geometric routing.

Fig. 6. Hardware proxemics and avoidance boundaries evaluated via Minimum Proxemic Clearance. (A) Static embodiment penalty, demonstrating the interaction effect: the absolute clearance (safety buffer) enforced by the table-mounted origin is highly magnified during converging (head-on) approaches. (B) Minimum proxemic clearance across dynamic trajectory profiles.

E. Covariate Analysis: Baseline Psychological Bias

Prior familiarity with virtual agents or video games did not significantly modulate reported cognitive load ($F(1, 46) = 0.04, p = 0.844$).

Subjective Covariates and Spatial Negotiation: To determine if baseline psychological apprehension dictated physical evasion, the Negative Attitudes Toward Robots Scale (NARS) Subscale 1 (Interaction Anxiety) was introduced as a covariate. Because the Likert anchors were established such that higher scores indicate disagreement with negative statements (1 = “I agree completely”, 5 = “I completely disagree”), higher numerical scores reflect lower baseline apprehension.

The LMM revealed a significant main effect of baseline apprehension on physical trajectory routing (Estimate = -6.56 , 95% CI [$-12.18, -0.93$], $p = 0.027, R_m^2 = 0.087$). Specifically, participants reporting lower *a priori* apprehension toward robots (higher NARS scores) exhibited a significantly tighter max spatial envelope. On the other hand, participants with higher baseline anxiety maintained significantly larger

spatial safety buffers, enforcing a wider lateral operational footprint during dynamic conflict. This confirms that physical proxemic adaptation is modulated not only by instantaneous kinematic conflict, but by the human’s baseline psychological comfort with the robotic agent.

IV. DISCUSSION

Our findings show that human spatial negotiation in HRC is a structured sequence of behavioral adaptations rather than a monolithic response to a robot’s presence. Aligning our findings with computational models of sensorimotor control allows us to evaluate these macroscopic penalties across three distinct interaction phases: the baseline perception of the workspace, the cognitive planning required to navigate spatial conflict, and the macroscopic execution of the avoidance behavior. As defined in our operational framework, the term “penalty” serves strictly as a macroscopic behavioral descriptor (e.g., expanded spatial envelopes, disrupted timing) and does not imply a specific internal optimization process within the human central nervous system.

Within this framework, the robot’s physical hardware mounting acts as a static contextual constraint. While table-mounted configurations were associated with implicitly expanded baseline proxemic safety margins, they merely establish the spatial stage. The acute behavioral penalties, specifically the elevated cognitive load and the disruption of temporal synchronization, are driven by the dynamic interference of the robot’s trajectory.

Our data indicate that these dynamic penalties are highly context-dependent, emerging primarily when Rectilinear trajectories intersect the human’s operational workspace during converging, opposite-side approaches. Parallel continuous kinematic analyses of this paradigm indicate that these categorical spatial effects covary strongly with a continuous geometric-conflict metric, wherein structural movement variance expands in direct proportion to the directional incongruency between the human and robot velocity vectors [21].

Optimizing collaborative efficiency therefore requires a dual-axis approach: planners must account for both the static baseline constraints of the hardware’s perceived spatial footprint (Perception) and the dynamic temporal-spatial conflict introduced by orthogonal kinematic transitions (Planning and Execution).

A. Behavioral Adaptation in Shared Workspaces

Evaluating the robot’s physical embodiment alongside its movement revealed a complex interaction between explicit perception and implicit motor adaptation. The table-mounted footprint was associated with an implicit expansion of the human’s safety margin without significantly elevating conscious psychological disturbance. Importantly, this physical embodiment penalty did not act independently; it was heavily magnified during converging spatial conflicts, mirroring the acute cognitive penalties associated with Rectilinear trajectories and the motor interference inherent to incongruent spatial motion [22], [23].

By evaluating these dimensions simultaneously, we quantified how static hardware constraints are associated with amplified dynamic kinematic penalties. The continuous kinematic signatures accompanying these macro-level adaptations are examined in our parallel analysis [21]. Consequently, future human-aware path planners must account for both the static footprint of the hardware and the dynamic, context-dependent legibility of the software [24].

B. Observed Behavioral Trade-offs in Trajectory Planning

The data formalize a behavioral trade-off in collaborative trajectory optimization, showing that this trade-off is highly context-dependent. Prior work emphasizes that a robot’s motion should be predictable and legible to the human collaborator [9]. In our study, Rectilinear paths minimized absolute Euclidean distance, but this algorithmic efficiency corresponded to measurable human penalties: a systematic expansion of the max spatial envelope, elevated cognitive load, and significantly disrupted temporal coordination.

Our interaction analysis demonstrated, however, that these penalties emerge primarily during converging, opposite-side approaches. When the robot approaches parallel to the human, algorithmic efficiency does not disrupt unhindered routing, supporting previous investigations into whether industrial robots should move directly or utilize spatial detours [25].

Curvilinear trajectories, despite consuming a larger absolute planar area, were associated with more direct human routing patterns and more continuous simultaneous motion during those high-conflict converging interactions. Although participants rated these paths as significantly more “human-like” on the PCEQ, subjective interpretations of anthropomorphism often lack consistent baseline definitions and are heavily influenced by the operator’s subjective task load during cooperative movements [26]. Rather than indicating true biological mimicry, these ratings likely reflect a preference for predictable, minimum-jerk motion profiles [18], [27], which have been experimentally validated to improve physical human-robot coordination [28]. One possible geometric explanation for this preference is that Curvilinear paths visually clear the shared workspace earlier. By yielding the transport corridor sooner, the robot may reduce the human’s perceived collision risk through spatial predictability rather than strictly biological motion.

C. Embodiment and Perceived Occupancy

Proxemic theory states that people naturally project spatial boundaries around robotic agents [29]. The data demonstrate that mounting location alters this perceived spatial occupancy, establishing a rigid static embodiment penalty. The table-mounted origin was associated with a measurable, implicit expansion of the human’s absolute safety boundary (minimum proxemic clearance) compared to the shoulder-mounted configuration, despite the absence of a conscious psychological disturbance [30].

Although this physical response represents a compound reaction to height, looming, approach angle, and base occlusion rather than a single isolated perceptual variable, it accurately

reflects the operational trade-offs of distinct mounting configurations in applied industrial settings.

Within this paradigm, high-conflict converging approaches corresponded to a significant expansion of the human’s max spatial envelope by nearly 48mm. Since operators primarily negotiate these lateral clearances by adjusting their arm posture, this spatial expansion directly aligns with recent findings that robot kinematics correspond to measurable motor interference in human elbow and limb configurations [31].

While acute spatial expansions of this magnitude are geometrically minor, motor control literature suggests their accumulation in repetitive, synchronized industrial tasks implicates occupational ergonomics [32]. Because our 15-trial protocol cannot establish long-term injury mechanisms, future longitudinal studies incorporating electromyography (EMG) and joint-torque analysis are required to determine whether these acute spatial adaptations scale to cumulative ergonomic risks (e.g., exceeding critical RULA/REBA thresholds [33]).

D. Virtual Familiarity and Psychological Covariates

Prior familiarity with virtual agents or video games did not significantly mitigate reported cognitive load or reduce proxemic safety boundaries. Passive digital exposure offered no measurable transfer of spatial confidence during physical shared-workspace navigation.

On the other hand, higher baseline apprehension toward robots (measured via NARS Subscale 1 [13]) was associated with a significantly expanded max spatial envelope. Rather than freezing or adopting a constrained kinematic footprint, individuals with higher interaction anxiety exhibited exaggerated spatial evasions. This indicates that baseline psychological discomfort amplifies the physical spatial penalties, as anxious operators maintained a wider lateral operational envelope far beyond what the acute kinematic conflict strictly requires.

E. Implications for Human-Aware Planning

To translate these empirical observations into applied control architectures, the synthesis framework (Figure 7) formalizes how spatial adaptations can be integrated into standard multi-objective cost functions. The total cost of a generated trajectory $\mathbf{p}_r(t)$ can be modeled as:

$$J_{\text{total}} = w_1 J_{\text{efficiency}} + w_2 J_{\text{embodiment}} + w_3 J_{\text{kinematic}} \quad (4)$$

where $J_{\text{efficiency}}$ encapsulates standard robotic constraints (e.g., path length, joint limits). The empirically derived behavioral penalties translate into these differentiable, time-varying costs:

Static Embodiment Cost ($J_{\text{embodiment}}$): To reflect the expanded proxemic boundaries associated with table-mounted origins, we define an origin-dependent spatial barrier evaluated continuously along the trajectory:

$$J_{\text{embodiment}} = \int_0^T c_{\text{rep}}(\|\mathbf{p}_r(t) - \mathbf{p}_h(t)\|, \epsilon_{\text{origin}}) dt \quad (5)$$

Following Khatib’s repulsive potential [34], let $d = \|\mathbf{p}_r(t) - \mathbf{p}_h(t)\|$. An illustrative heuristic is $c_{\text{rep}} =$

$\frac{1}{2}k \left(\frac{1}{d} - \frac{1}{\epsilon_{\text{origin}}} \right)^2$ when $d \leq \epsilon_{\text{origin}}$, and 0 otherwise. Based on our findings, the influence threshold (ϵ_{origin}) requires a larger scalar parameter for table-mounted architectures. Mirroring the interaction effect observed in our data, this threshold cannot be uniformly radial; it must be dynamically magnified when the relative velocity vectors indicate a converging spatial conflict.

Dynamic Kinematic Cost ($J_{\text{kinematic}}$): To mitigate the cognitive load, disrupted temporal coordination, and expansion of the max spatial envelope associated with Rectilinear intrusions, we propose penalties for kinematic smoothness and directional alignment:

$$J_{\text{kinematic}} = \int_0^T \left[\lambda_1 \|\ddot{\mathbf{p}}_r(t)\|^2 + \lambda_2 f_{\text{align}}(\mathbf{v}_r(t), \mathbf{v}_h(t)) \right] dt \quad (6)$$

The first term penalizes high-jerk profiles ($\ddot{\mathbf{p}}_r$), encouraging the Curvilinear routing shown to preserve human path efficiency (η). The second term formalizes spatial conflict. To penalize converging (opposite-side) approaches, a directional dot product provides a functional heuristic: $f_{\text{align}} = \max(0, -(\mathbf{v}_r(t) \cdot \mathbf{v}_h(t)))$.

Translational Scope: These equations provide conceptual mappings rather than deployable control laws. Implementing these formulations requires addressing standard control-theoretic challenges (e.g., convexity, differentiability, and on-line state estimation). Because this study focuses on behavioral measurement, these formalisms serve strictly to bridge our empirical findings with the structural language of trajectory optimization [35].

F. Limitations and Alternative Explanations

Although this study evaluates acute spatial avoidance under controlled conditions, a few boundaries limit its generalizability. First, the sample consisted primarily of a university cohort ($M_{\text{age}} = 24.2$ years); validation in applied industrial populations is necessary. Second, the experiment employed a lightweight UR3 cobot. Spatial adaptation may scale nonlinearly with heavier manipulators (e.g., UR10) that present different inertia profiles and perceived kinetic risks. Third, the paradigm relied on a deterministic rhythm; these behavioral trade-offs must be evaluated in non-deterministic assembly scenarios.

Although our operational framework separates static embodiment and dynamic kinematic penalties, physical hardware manipulation remains inherently bundled. Altering the hardware origin does not isolate a single morphological variable; rather, this shift simultaneously manipulates mounting height, visual saliency, perceived looming, and workspace geometry. Consequently, the observed baseline proxemic expansion (quantified via minimum proxemic clearance) reflects the compound effect of distinct *physical mounting configurations* typical of industrial settings, rather than a single perceptual variable. Future research using virtual or augmented reality (VR/AR) could systematically decouple these factors to pinpoint the specific psychological drivers of spatial adaptation.

It is also critical to acknowledge the mechanical constraints inherent to the trajectory generation utilized in this paradigm. To isolate the spatial geometry of the motion from temporal

Fig. 7. Conceptual synthesis mapping the empirical pipeline. Experimental system inputs (Layer 1) correspond to dissociable spatial and cognitive human adaptations (Layer 2), including a profound interaction where spatial congruency magnifies the static embodiment penalty. These behavioral responses provide empirical priors to inform human-aware mathematical costs in future multi-objective trajectory optimizers (Layer 3).

confounds, both profiles were locked to an identical cycle time ($t = 2.0$ s). Consequently, the Rectilinear manipulation necessarily coupled an orthogonal path geometry with elevated peak kinematics (roughly 20% higher peak velocity) and a complete intermediate stop at the via-point. Therefore, the present findings regarding the max spatial envelope and cognitive workload must be interpreted as behavioral responses to this bundled, distinctly more aggressive trajectory condition, rather than the isolated effect of pure geometric shape alone. Future work isolating velocity from path curvature will be required to decouple these variables.

It is also necessary to contextualize the magnitude of the observed effects. While the fixed-effect variance explained by the interaction of trajectory shape and spatial congruency on cognitive load is objectively small ($R_m^2 = 0.024$), this is expected in continuous human-subjects research where individual biomechanical and psychological noise inherently dominates. However, in industrial automation, marginal acute increases in cognitive load or max spatial envelope expansion scale significantly when compounded over repetitive, multi-hour assembly shifts.

Finally, although SMR employs a discrete Boolean threshold, future work could explore continuous phase-synchronization metrics. For discrete pick-and-place tasks, however, Boolean detection remains better suited for quantifying the episodic pausing patterns that are often obscured by continuous coupling coefficients.

V. CONCLUSION

This study provides empirical evidence that, within a synchronized collaborative task, human spatial avoidance behavior acts as a dual-axis spatial negotiation, modulated simultaneously by the static physical footprint of the robot and the dynamic geometry of its trajectory. By isolating these factors, we operationalized two macro-level behavioral baselines for human-aware motion planning.

First, we demonstrated that standard Rectilinear trajectories, while algorithmically efficient, are associated with a significant dynamic behavioral penalty on the human operator. These trajectories corresponded to elevated cognitive load, disrupted temporal coordination, and a reliable expansion of the human's max spatial envelope.

However, we found that these penalties are highly context-dependent, emerging primarily during converging, opposite-side approaches. Implementing Curvilinear routing during these specific high-conflict interactions was associated with reduced envelope expansions, preserving human kinematic efficiency and task precision.

Second, we observed that a robot's hardware origin corresponds to a subconscious static embodiment penalty. While table-mounted configurations do not significantly elevate subconscious psychological disturbance, they were associated with implicitly expanded proxemic safety margins (absolute 3D Euclidean clearance) compared to shoulder-mounted systems.

Reflecting the dynamic behavioral penalty, this physical embodiment penalty was heavily amplified during converging spatial conflicts.

In summary, shortest-path kinematics alone cannot optimize collaborative efficiency. To bridge the gap between geometric collision avoidance and true ergonomic collaboration, future trajectory planners and predictive controllers should natively integrate both the physical embodiment of the hardware and the context-dependent, multi-axis spatial boundaries of the human operator. A complementary analysis of the same experimental dataset investigates the continuous variance structure and biomechanical correlates underlying these behavioral effects [21].

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no financial or commercial conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

APPENDIX

This appendix provides the comprehensive descriptive statistics, detailing the raw unadjusted means (M) and standard deviations (SD) for all primary objective and subjective measures analyzed in this study. Data are aggregated across the core experimental manipulations: Hardware Origin, Trajectory Shape, and Spatial Congruency.

TABLE A-I
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS FOR KINEMATIC, PROXEMIC, AND PERFORMANCE MEASURES

Hardware (Origin)	Software (Shape / Direction)	Min. Clearance <i>M (SD) mm</i>	Max Spatial Env. <i>M (SD) mm</i>	Drop Area <i>M (SD) mm²</i>	Simult. Motion <i>M (SD) %</i>
Shoulder	Curvilinear / Same-side	188.3 (9.9)	73.8 (68.9)	111.0 (126.0)	86.0 (5.4)
	Curvilinear / Opposite-side	211.7 (21.0)	114.0 (86.6)	76.4 (91.1)	87.1 (4.9)
	Rectilinear / Same-side	191.3 (10.7)	62.2 (69.9)	94.9 (79.3)	82.2 (5.5)
	Rectilinear / Opposite-side	205.6 (19.7)	133.0 (111.4)	120.0 (198.0)	79.3 (7.8)
Table	Curvilinear / Same-side	190.4 (9.2)	74.2 (61.4)	101.0 (93.6)	87.3 (4.7)
	Curvilinear / Opposite-side	219.8 (21.5)	91.0 (72.5)	71.3 (74.1)	87.0 (5.3)
	Rectilinear / Same-side	190.6 (9.6)	71.6 (73.5)	114.0 (94.1)	81.7 (6.0)
	Rectilinear / Opposite-side	211.9 (19.3)	125.9 (107.7)	113.0 (101.0)	78.9 (7.4)

Note: Min. Clearance = *Minimum Proxemic Clearance*; Max Spatial Env. = *Max Spatial Envelope*; Drop Area = *2D Planar Endpoint Precision Area*; Simult. Motion = *Simultaneous Motion Ratio (SMR)*.

TABLE A-II
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS FOR SUBJECTIVE COGNITIVE LOAD (NASA-TLX) AND PCEQ MEASURES

Hardware (Origin)	Software (Shape / Direction)	Mental <i>M (SD)</i>	Temporal <i>M (SD)</i>	Frust. <i>M (SD)</i>	Overall <i>M (SD)</i>	Sync. Diff. <i>M (SD)</i>	Human-like <i>M (SD)</i>
Shoulder	Curv. / Same	27.10 (19.90)	26.20 (21.50)	18.80 (13.70)	26.50 (17.20)	1.75 (0.91)	2.88 (1.06)
	Curv. / Opp.	30.40 (22.20)	27.20 (20.50)	20.70 (16.80)	27.70 (18.00)	1.90 (1.04)	2.94 (1.00)
	Rect. / Same	23.80 (16.50)	26.70 (21.10)	19.00 (14.10)	25.00 (14.50)	1.73 (0.76)	2.21 (1.15)
	Rect. / Opp.	36.50 (23.00)	30.90 (21.80)	26.50 (20.90)	32.90 (18.50)	2.67 (1.08)	1.96 (1.07)
Table	Curv. / Same	23.40 (18.00)	25.90 (19.00)	16.90 (14.40)	24.60 (15.20)	1.77 (0.83)	2.85 (1.11)
	Curv. / Opp.	28.60 (20.10)	28.30 (21.20)	19.70 (16.60)	27.30 (15.50)	2.02 (0.93)	2.77 (1.02)
	Rect. / Same	26.20 (19.80)	26.70 (19.90)	20.40 (16.40)	26.40 (16.60)	1.96 (1.03)	1.92 (0.99)
	Rect. / Opp.	33.10 (24.10)	31.20 (22.50)	23.20 (16.50)	30.40 (17.00)	2.50 (1.11)	1.92 (0.96)

Note: Overall = Raw TLX unweighted mean; Sync. Diff. = PCEQ “Harder to Synchronize With”; Human-like = PCEQ “Perceived as Human-like”. Curv. = Curvilinear; Rect. = Rectilinear; Opp. = Opposite-side.

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